

Consensus based phase connectivity identification for distribution network with limited observability

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Abstract

The mitigation of distribution network (DN) unbalance and the use of single-phase flexibility for congestion mitigation requires accurate phase connection information, which is often not available. For a large DN, the naïve phase identification proposed in the majority of the prior works using a single voltage reference, this does not scale well for a multi-feeder DN. We present a consensus algorithm-based phase identification mechanism which uses multiple three-phase reference points to improve the prediction of phases. Due to the absence of real measurements for a real-suburban German DN, the algorithms are developed and evaluated over synthetic data using a digital twin. To utilize strongly correlated measurements, the DN is clustered into zones. We observe those reference measurements located in the same zone as the single-phase consumer, with unknown phase connectivity, leads to accurate prediction of DN phases. Four consensus algorithms are developed and compared. Using numerical results, we recommend the most robust phase identification mechanism. In our evaluation, measurement error, and the impact of the neutral conductor are also assessed. We assume limited DN observability and apply our findings to a German DN without smart meters, but only less than 8% of nodes have measurement boxes along with single-phase consumers with a home energy management system. Voltage time series for 1 month (hourly sampled) is utilized. The numerical results indicate that for 1% accuracy class measurement, the phase connectivity of 308 out of 313 single-phase consumers in a German DN can be identified. Further, we also propose metrics quantifying the goodness of the phase identification. The phase identification framework based on consensus algorithms for DN zones is scalable for large DN and robust towards measurement errors as the estimation is not dependent on a single measurement point.

Index Terms

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I. INTRODUCTION

The low voltage distribution network (DN) in Europe consists predominantly of single phase (1- ϕ) loads, inverter interfaced PV, storage, and electric vehicle charging infrastructure. The penetration level of these devices is expected to grow further in the future, as they are considered enablers of

NOMENCLATURE

Operators

\bar{K}	Mean value of vector K
J_x	PCI metric
S_0	Naïve model
S_y	Consensus algorithms for $y \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ ‘
β_c	Voltage threshold for clsuter c
N	Set of nodes in the DN
$\phi \in \{A, B, C\}$	Connection phase
c	Cluster id
E	Set of edges in the DN graph
L_c	Number of 1- ϕ consumers in clsuter c
M_c	Number of measurement points in clsuter c
N_c	Number of nodes in clsuter c
$t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$	Time ‘

Variables and parameters

$\bar{A}_c^{Jx, Sy}$	Mean estimation accuracy in % for metric Jx and consensus algorithm Sy
$\bar{F}_c^{Jx, Sy}$	Mean confidence factor for metric Jx and consensus algorithm Sy
$\rho_{Jx}^{c, i_c^M(j)}$	Correlation matrix based on reference voltage at node $i_c^M(j)$ and metric $Tx, x \in \{1, 2, 3\}$
$P_c^{\text{est}, Jx, Sy}$	Estimated phase of N_c 1- ϕ consumers in cluster c for metric Jx and consensus algo. Sy
$V_{i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}}$	Reference 3- ϕ voltage matrix based on measurement at node $i_c^M(j)$
V_c^L	1- ϕ load matrix of N_c customers in cluster c
$V_{\phi, i, t}$	Voltage at node i , phase ϕ , time t
$Y_{\phi, i, j}$	Admittance of branch $i, j \in N$, phase ϕ
$D_c^{Jx, Sy}$	Sensitivity factor for metrix Jx and consensus algorithm Sy

the green energy transition in EU-level targets such as Fit-for-55 [1]. Often the phase connectivity of such resources is not accurately known. This lack of DN observability will restrict the monitoring and control of DN imbalances. Existing DN consists of multiple measurements at the feeder level and end of the feeder, which provides utilities with some degree of observability. The goal of the paper is to develop a scalable and robust phase connectivity identification (PCI) framework that considers multiple measurement points for improving the PCI.

Phase identification methodologies can be broadly classified as intrusive and non-intrusive. As the name suggests, intrusive methods require manual identification of phases and are often labor-intensive and/or hardware-based [2]. On the other hand, non-intrusive methods are often data-driven. A brief summary of non-intrusive phase identification methods is detailed in Table I. These data-driven methods can be classified based on the parameter and tool used for PCI. For the literature summarized in Table I, the classification is presented in Fig. 1. From Fig. 1, we observe that 64% of existing works utilize voltage magnitude time series and approximately 27% utilize correlation as a tool for PCI. In this work, we also utilize these widely used techniques for developing a consensus-based phase identification framework using voltage time series and correlation as the tool. Voltage time series-based PCI is more robust to limited observability in a DN, also observed in [3]. On the other hand, the power-based methods rely on the law of conservation of energy and require a high degree of observability in a DN. The research gap tackled in this paper is to develop a PCI framework considering multiple 3- ϕ measurement references for building consensus among different estimation outputs without the need for full observability in the DN.

Motivation: With the increasing penetration of 1- ϕ generation from renewable energy sources and the growing addition of flexible loads like electric vehicles, heat pumps, etc. congestions, voltage violations and phase imbalances in the grid will likely become more frequent. Therefore, suitable corrective measures must be found and implemented. An important basis for mitigation measures is the detection of congestions and thus, firstly, improving the network model of the low-voltage grid, which is still largely unmonitored in many parts of the world today. Accurate network topology is assumed to be known in many works [4], [5]. However, this assumption is not accurate in the case of EUniversal's demo networks for the German DN. The goal of this work is to develop a scalable and robust PCI framework for improving DN topology information. This will assist system operators to plan, activate and schedule DN flexibility resources.

TABLE I: Literature review on non-intrusive phase identification

Ref	Measurement needs	Proposed solution	Remarks	Methodology	Input
[6]	AMI voltage time series, partially incorrect phase label information	Spectral clustering with a sliding window; does not require substation measurement	91% accuracy, Google street view analyzed for phase identification	Clustering / Un-supervised ML	voltage
[7]	Voltage magnitude (denoted as $ V $)	Spectral clustering is utilized and MILP model is used for unbalance mitigation.	156 user DN in China is used for validation. Majority rule is applied to over predictions over new data.	Clustering / Un-supervised ML	voltage
[8]	Voltage magnitude	k-means clustering with Gaussian Mixture Model algorithm for phase id	91% accurate; with salient features accuracy is 100%	Clustering / Un-supervised ML	voltage
[9]	Voltage magnitude	k-means clustering is used. Use multiple references with Majority rule based estimation.	90% accuracy	Clustering / Un-supervised ML	voltage
[10]	Voltage magnitude	k-medoids clustering is with denoised data	Singular value decomposition is used for denoising	Clustering / Un-supervised ML	voltage
[11]	Voltage magnitude	principal components are used to extract feature vectors over which constrained k-means clustering is applied	90% accuracy	Clustering / Un-supervised ML	voltage
[12]	Voltage magnitude	k-means clustering with principal component analysis	Phase identification is applied for multiple days separately and a majority rule is applied	Clustering / Un-supervised ML	voltage
[13]	Active power measurements, substation as reference	extract distinct features from load profiles and correlate with phase load; limitation: high granularity data needed	93% accuracy with 10% SMs in DN; results compared with [14]	Correlation	power
[15]	Voltage magnitude	Correlation based; the salient features of the time series are extracted.	Large enough data sheet leads to 100% accuracy for 75 consumer DN	Correlation	voltage
[16]	Voltage magnitude	Relies on graph theory and the notion of maximum spanning tree. Correlation based PCI for a four wire DN.	Closer the measurement points are geographically, the stronger the correlation between the voltages	Correlation	voltage
[17]	Voltage magnitude	Difference matrix is created	82% accuracy	Correlation	voltage
[18]	Voltage magnitude time series	Correlation between voltage measurements of SMs with constrained k-means	substation voltage is used as reference for phase identification	Correlation with unsupervised ML	voltage
[19]	Active power and voltage time series data	Correlationship with clustering is performed. Ensemble learning combines voltage and power-based estimation results.	Impact of different SM accuracy class is evaluated	Correlation with unsupervised ML	voltage and power

Ref	Measurement needs	Proposed solution	Remarks	Methodology	Input
[14]	Active power time series at the transformer and consumers	integer programming along with branch and bound search algorithm. Access sensitivity of the ratio of measurement points and total number of consumers	MILP based solution depends on the principle of conservation of energy.	Optimization	power
[20]	P, Q and $ V $ measurements	MILP with Bender's decomposition is used. Accuracy of phase id is governed by number of data points, SM class, data resolution	For large EU feeder, the runtime with 5% SM error is 39.2 hours. Difficult to scale.	Optimization	power (P & Q) and voltage
[21]	P, Q, $ V $ measurements	Utilize state-estimation with MILP, also considers errors in layout information	Data needs are smaller compared to statistical and ML-based techniques	Optimization	power and voltage
[22]	Active power time series	LASSO based data driven approach. Also considers SM accuracy class	97% accuracy with 60% SMs; LASSO immune to noise unlike [14]	Statistical or ML	power
[23]– [25]	Energy measurement time series	data-driven approach with Principal component analysis & graph theory interpretations	Also considers noisy data	Statistical or ML	power
[26]	Voltage magnitude time series	Develops multi-dimensional calibration in phase id based on voltage characteristics in LVDN	Observe that voltage characteristics are more robust under incomplete data	Statistical or ML	voltage
[27]	Voltage magnitude	Linear regression and voltage drop relationship for phase identification	Observe close measurement are strongly correlated	Statistical or ML	voltage
[24]	Voltage phasor time series measured using microPMUs	Phase id analyses cross correlations over voltage magnitudes and detects the phase angle difference between reference and test nodes	multi-phase connections are also considered. Fine resolution of 120 samples per sec is used	Statistical or ML	voltage phasor
[28]	P, $ V $ time series	Using statistical analysis of AMI data over a day for DN with PV. Regression model is used to model substation voltage using nodal P, V and substation power.	Explore data needs, granularity and impact of PV penetration levels	Statistical or ML	voltage and power
[29]	Voltage magnitude and phase info of a small representative set	Train an ML model of constrained function of voltage time series. Since manual measurements are needed thus may not be scalable	5% selected representative set leads to accuracy of 91.9%	Statistical or ML	voltage
[30]	Voltage phasor time series	Use sequence component for phase identification	Also utilize SM data for learning the topology of the DN	Statistical or ML	voltage phasor
[31]	Voltage magnitude	Supervised machine learning with theory of information loss	Accuracy up to 97%	Supervised ML	
[32]	Voltage phasor time series	Topology and phase identification using linearized model of three-phase unbalanced DN.	120 Hz PMU measurements are used. Data collected for 1 second to 1 minute is used for estimation	Statistical or ML	voltage phasors

Fig. 1: Classifying of phase connectivity identification literature based on parameter(s) and tool(s) used.

A. Contributions and observations of the paper

The contributions and observations are as follows:

- A tailor-made solution for the German DSO, Mitnetz Strom, is proposed for PCI, which considers multiple measurements in a DN zone for improving the estimation accuracy. The schematic for proposed PCI is shown in Fig. 2. The proposed framework can also be applied to other DNs with limited DN observability.
- Twelve phase identification models are benchmarked over the naïve PCI model. The naïve model considers only one $3 - \phi$ measurement reference in a DN for phase estimation. The proposed phase identification models build a consensus among multiple measurements for robust phase estimation.
- Metrics are proposed for evaluating phase identification models using (a1) accuracy of estimation, (a2) confidence factor, and (a3) sensitivity towards measurement errors. Metrics (a2) and (a3) provide a qualitative metric for evaluating estimation accuracy.
- A detailed description is provided for synthetic data generation, which utilizes an example suburban LV DN grid model of Mitnetz Strom. Digital twin-based synthetic data generation is also crucial for DNs with limited or no historical measurement data.
- Four case studies are performed in the numerical results. The performance of the naïve model is used for benchmarking and comparing the proposed phase identification algorithms.

- Firstly, the proposed PCI models using consensus algorithms are compared in context of the real German DN. The naïve PCI model is used for benchmarking.
- Secondly, we quantify the impact of measurement proximity on phase identification metrics. We observe that for a DN partitioned into zones, the estimation quality deteriorates as the measurement reference selected is farther away from the zone where the consumer is located.
- Thirdly, the impact of measurement errors on PCI is assessed. For 1% accuracy class measurements, an estimation accuracy exceeding 98.6% is achieved for a DN with 646 nodes.
- Most European DNs are a four-wire system. In our last case study, we quantify the impact of the neutral conductor model on phase estimation accuracy. We observe that if the neutral conductor is not modeled, then a pessimistic estimation is achieved. Based on the knowledge of the authors, the neutral conductor impact assessment is done for the first time.

Fig. 2: Consensus-based PCI, synthetic data generation and metrics used

Although, this work exclusively deals with 1- ϕ consumer phase connectivity identification, the extension of this methodology to 3- ϕ consumers is not difficult. A 3- ϕ consumer can be considered as three independent 1- ϕ consumers, and in that case we can directly apply our findings in this paper directly. The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the German DN case of low observability and the need for enhanced phase information for future DN operation. Section III outlines the different modeling steps used for generating synthetic data used for phase connectivity identification. Section IV presents the methodology, and Section V presents the consensus algorithms

used for phase identification. Section VI presents the four numerical case studies, and section VII concludes the paper.

II. LOW OBSERVABILITY IN DN: THE GERMAN CASE

The low voltage grid serves households and small consumers connecting at 230 or 400 V [33]. German authorities have decided to implement an optional smart meter (SM) roll-out as the information security standards need to be adjusted. Presently, less than 5% of residential customers in Germany are equipped with SMs [34], [35]. Thus, the smart meter infrastructure is not widespread at a low-voltage level. The German Energy Industry Act requires that customers with a yearly consumption of over 6000 kWh are provided with smart measurement systems (when technically possible) [36], [37]. The requirement also applies to generators with an installed capacity above 7 kW. However, these requirements leave the majority of German households unaffected. The lack of sufficiently granular metering equipment at the household level is currently a barrier to implementing imbalance-sensitive flexibility activation for solving DN issues.

A. Metering of German DN

Mitnetz Strom is one of the largest regional distribution system operators in Eastern Germany and is responsible for supplying electricity to 2.2 million electricity consumers. The grid area of Mitnetz Strom covers an area of 30,804 km² and is characterized by rural conditions with a high share of renewables. The installed capacity of renewable energy reached an all-time high of more than 10,000 MW (more than 64,000 plants) in 2021. This development was spurred primarily by rapid growth in solar energy, as the number of photovoltaic installations increased by more than 17 %. [38].

In Germany, the metering and DSO roles are decoupled. The Meter Point Operator (MPO) is responsible for the installation, operation, data gathering, and maintenance of energy meters. Note, in many locations, system operators also perform as MPO. However, the electricity consumer could opt for an independent MPO. This is in accordance with the § 43 German MsbG (measuring point operation law). In principle, also a third party can be commissioned as a meter operator with the operation of the metering point on the free market [39]. Furthermore, there is presently no general legal obligation to share grid-relevant information obtained from smart meters with the DSO. Due to these constraints, DSO needs to request for receiving historical data thus cannot be utilized for short-term grid operation, congestion mitigation, etc (due to delays in DSO making a request and receiving the measurement data). *Thus, observability in DNs are limited not only by SM penetration level but also by data-sharing policies targeting system operators.* Appendix A details the metering infrastructure rollout plan for Germany till the year 2032.

B. Demo network for EUniversal

In EUniversal, Mitnetz Strom is testing the use of flexibility services and markets and is leading the German demonstration together with the parent company E.ON SE [40]. The German demonstration tries to combine principles of the German mandatory process Redispatch 2.0 [41] and a market-based approach to mitigate grid constraints in a cascaded operation across multiple voltage levels. The goal is to provide DSOs with access to flexibility from grid customers across the LV/MV level for their active system management. To this end, the EUniversal consortium is testing various optimization algorithms with the aim of minimizing activation costs while ensuring the secure operation of the grid and is developing concepts for grid state estimation of smart grids, of which the first interim results and experiences will be presented. In the German demo of EUniversal, Mitnetz Strom and its partners are investigating the use of flexibility markets in low voltage grids for congestion management and voltage maintenance. An attempt is being made to develop an iterative procedure that will prevent new congestion from occurring when flexibility is activated.

1) *Network features and meter placement:* The network considered for numerical evaluation is a typical low-voltage network in Mitnetz's network area in a small town in Eastern Germany. There are already some plants that could be used as a flexibility (e.g. batteries, EVs) but the penetration level of the devices are yet not significant. Due to application cases, certain locations in the LV grid are particularly interesting when it comes to equipping with measurement technology. In particular, the end of the feeder is often an important indicator for the evaluation of potential voltage band violations, while the current at the beginning of the feeder is important for the thermal constraints in the network. Unfortunately, these points are often not available in practice due to ownership issues and the partially pronounced building development in the localities. Therefore, *cable distribution cabinets* were selected and equipped with measurement devices used for generating reference 3- ϕ voltage measurements. For EUniversal devices are a bundle of voltage and current sensors (Rogowski coils), gateway, and power supply. As mentioned previously, the SM penetration in the German DN is less than 5%, therefore, home energy management system (HEMS) boxes are distributed for consumers willing to offer their flexibility for probable congestion mitigation. The HEMS boxes acts as 1- ϕ measurement devices that output the voltage time series. This voltage measurement at consumer end is used for estimating the phase connectivity of that 1- ϕ consumer.

Fig. 3: Accurate phase information leads to improved DN topology information, leading the listed applications.

TABLE II: Need for phase connectivity identification

	Role	References
General usage	Topology detection	[42]
	3- ϕ unbalance analysis	[43]
	Grid visualization	-
	State estimation	[44]
	Power flow analysis	[45]
Operational application	1- ϕ flexibility activation	[5]
	Unbalance compensation	[46]
	Load balancing	[47]
Planning application	Phase selection for DN resources	[48]
	Reassigning phases	[49]

C. Need for phase information

LV DN topology identification is essential for efficient network operation, monitoring, and control. This also assists in planning the phases for new resources connected to the DN. In Appendix B, a real-world case is summarized, showcasing the improved utilization of DN by more than 30% with timely balancing of 1- ϕ electric vehicle load. Table II summarizes the different needs for the phase information. In the case of flexibility markets, this means the possibility of using flexibility decreases for ensuring grid integrity. This underlines the importance of having accurate knowledge of the phase connections, as flexibility activation should not further increase imbalance. In theory, flexibility activation could also limit DN imbalance. Mitnetz Strom and most DSO's follow a passive way of identifying the phase connections. The accurate topology identification is performed manually in case of a follow-up on customer complaints on power quality. This motivates us to propose a scalable and robust phase identification mechanism using historical measurement data.

III. SYNTHETIC DATA GENERATION

In this section, we detail the steps we took to generate synthetic data for the DSO grid layout provided in DigSilent format. A digital twin is used for the process of phase and load placement. Further, the neutral conductor modeling, noise injection, and zonal clustering model used in this work are elaborated in this section.

A. DGS parser for network JSON

A parser has been created to convert the DGS (DigSilent) [50] file format into a JSON file that is readable to the PowerModels script. The parser is derived from the GridCal python package [51]. The main difference between the two formats is that the DGS data format contains different classes with different information in a hierarchical structure, whereas the JSON file just requires information on the buses, branches, and devices in the grid.

1) *Bus information:* The DGS format relies on cubicle information, which can be seen as a connection point for the different elements in the grid. The cubicle information is the unique identification number given to each connection point.

2) *Branch information:* The DGS branch format relies on cable type information, but the JSON file requires the values directly in per-unit (pu). Therefore, the r and x parameters (amongst other) needs to be converted from their ohmic values to pu of the total cable length.

3) *Device information:* The DGS file format contains detailed information on different loads and/or generators. The JSON file format only has information on the devices. Therefore, the parser extracts the relevant P and Q data from each device in the DGS file and compiles it as a separate entity in the device file. Additional information included are bus ID, PV size, and connected phase.

4) *Switches:* A crucial element of the parser is removing the switches that connect branches to substations and cabins. The switches are removed as they add numerical complexities when calculating the admittance matrix in PowerModels [52]. Setting the r and x values to zero can lead to infinity values during the admittance calculation, but setting it to a very low value (≈ 0) leads to inefficiencies when running the power flow. Removal of the switches not only removes numerical complexities but, since switches make up 7% of the nodes in the system, by removing the extra nodes the computation time of the simulation significantly increases (in the order of a 10%).

B. Mitnetz Strom DN and metadata

The DN metadata contains details associated with different consumer devices in the grid. The information includes a node number to connect it to the grid data, load type (e.g. household, PV, CHP, etc.), the annual energy consumption, single or three-phase connection, and the available active and reactive power output (if applicable). The information is compiled and appended to the device's JSON file. Fig. 4 shows the spread of the annual cumulative energy consumption of loads connected to the test DN used in this work.

Note that the exact phase connection of single-phase loads is not known. The goal of this paper is to present a framework for identifying the phase connection of such single-phase consumers.

Fig. 4: Metadata for annual kWh consumption of 331 consumers in the test LV DN considered. Note that 94.5% of consumers have an annual consumption of lower than 6000 kWh for the test DN.

C. Randomized phase mapping

DSOs actively try to balance the phases so that the load distribution is fairly balanced. Madeira island case study in [53] and DSO questionnaire in [54] details the phase assignment procedure of a DSO.

In order to generate synthetic data, randomized load mapping is used. For a single phase load with different levels of annual kWh consumption, a phase is randomly selected from phases A, B, and C with equal likelihood.

Fig. 5: Phase load distribution of three-phase distribution network for 100000 phase mapping scenarios.

The randomized phase mapping is evaluated based on the sum of the absolute error in phase load (AEPL), given as

$$AEPL = \frac{1}{3} \frac{1}{D} \sum_{i=1}^D \sum_{\phi \in \{A,B,C\}} |L_{\phi}^D - \bar{L}^D|,$$

where D denotes the number of Monte Carlo phase mapping scenarios, and \bar{L}^D denotes the mean load in all the phases and is given as $\bar{L}^D = \sum_{\phi \in \{A,B,C\}} L_{\phi}^D / 3$.

Using 100000 Monte Carlo simulations for phase mapping, we observe that randomized phase mapping performs fairly well, with a maximum and mean per phase load deviation of 30% and 9.5% with respect to the mean load met by the three phases in the worst case (Fig. 6). Fig. 6 shows the distribution of the phase load errors while performing randomized phase mapping.

Thus, in this work, we utilize randomized phase mapping for data generation for evaluating our proposed probabilistic phase identification mechanism.

D. Neutral modelling for four-wire DN

European LV DN is usually different from the North-American one with a larger size distribution transformer with multiple low voltage feeders supplying a large number of consumers per trans-

Fig. 6: Sum of the absolute value of the difference of phase load and the mean load of all the phases.

In (??), $z_{l,aa}^s$ is self-impedance of the phase a of the branch l , $z_{l,nn}^s$ is self-impedance of the neutral of the branch l , and so on. Similarly, $z_{l,ab}^s$ is the mutual-impedance between phase a and b of branch l .

¹A perfectly grounded neutral refers to grounding resistance of zero ohms. Typically, the grounding resistance is ≈ 5 ohms, which leads to a small voltage drop. In this work, we assume perfectly grounded neutral.

Fig. 7: Isolated neutral model of distribution network

This transformation is exact and eliminates the error introduced by Kron's reduction in three-phase DN modeling for sparsely grounded system [57], [58]. Furthermore, a minor boost in computation time is achieved compared to the exact four-wire model as the necessity of carrying extra variables for neutral voltage is removed. This reduction is more relevant as the measured voltages in German demo-grid are also phase-to-neutral. Interested readers are guided to [57] for details about the transformation.

E. Metering noise injection model

Prior works [19], [20], [22], [25] consider smart meter measurement error based on the accuracy class of metering infrastructure. Frequently, the measurement error is considered using Gaussian noise. Further, the measurement accuracy is considered to hold true for three sigma of the times, which corresponds to 99.7% of total instances. The standard deviation of the Gaussian noise is related to the tolerance τ of the measuring device. The noisy measurement is given as

$$\hat{Z} = Z \times \text{Norm}(1, \tau/3), \quad (2)$$

where Z denotes the true measurement, $\text{Norm}(\mu, \sigma)$ denotes a sample of a normal distribution with mean μ and standard deviation σ . In order to evaluate the impact of measurement noise, 1000 Monte Carlo simulations are considered.

F. Zonal clustering of Mitnetz Strom DN

Identifying the zones of an LV DN can be helpful to the DSO in planning the flexibility needs of a network. Due to the large numbers of DN feeders, a standardized approach to divide zones based on electrical and/or geographical distances is deemed essential [59]. In this section, the summary of

the clustering framework to identify the best-suited LV DN zonal partition using electrical distance as a measure is presented, which is explained in detail in [59]. This zonal partition method uses an incidence matrix-based measure, which can be obtained with the help of spectral decomposition of the admittance matrix. The adequate number of zones are obtained based on the maximization of silhouette score while considering the desired number of clusters.

The zonal partition divides nodes \mathcal{N} into $c \in \{1, \dots, C\}$ clusters. The spectral clustering proposed in [60], [61] for the creation of zones or network reduction is used for zonal partition. A double stochastic matrix is formed, which is a special type of Markov matrix where not only each row but also each column add to 1. For this transformed matrix, all eigenvalues are real and smaller than or equal to 1, with one eigenvalue exactly equal to 1 [62]. For identifying C partitions in a graph, the C highest eigenvalues and corresponding orthonormal eigenvectors are identified. The eigenvector matrix of the order $N \times C$ is used for DN partitioning, in effect reduces the dimensionality of the problem. k -means clustering is used to partition the spectral data points. The goodness of a cluster is measured using the mean silhouette index of the network cluster. The silhouette coefficient of a node is a confidence indicator of its association in a group [60], [63].

1) *Distance measure for clustering:* A DN can be represented in standard directed graph notation $G = (N, E, W)$, where N denotes the set of nodes such that $|N| = D$ (D denotes the total number of nodes), E denotes edges and W denotes edge weight matrix. We aim to divide N into p groups $\{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_p\}$ such that $M_i \subset N$ and $M_i \cap M_j = \emptyset, \forall i \neq j$. The edge weights can be considered a penalty for cutting that line in the graph while clustering. It also measures the connection strength of two nodes in a graph. A good measure would separate the weakly connected nodes and identify nodes that should be clustered together. A power network can be clustered based on static network parameters such as line impedance/admittance or dynamic parameters such as power flows, line losses, and voltage variations [61], [64], [65]. The electrical distance matrix is used for partitioning LV DNs in [61], [66]. Similar to these prior works, we use the line admittance matrix as the distance measure parameter. The weight $w_{ij} = Y_{ij} = 1/|R_{ij} + jX_{ij}|$, where Y_{ij} , R_{ij} and X_{ij} denotes admittance, resistance and impedance between nodes i and j and the edge weight $w : N \times N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\geq 0}$ such that (a) $w_{ij} = w_{ji}, \forall i, j$, (b) $w_{ij} = 0$, if $(i, j) \notin E$, (c) $w_{ii} = 0, \forall i$.

2) *Spectral partitioning:* Spectral clustering is used for power network partitioning or creation of zones or network reduction in [60], [61]. The previously described weight matrix cannot be directly used, as the diagonal elements are all zeros. Authors in [61] use the normalized Laplacian matrix for

spectral partitioning. Tutorial [67] transforms the weight matrix into a doubly stochastic matrix. A double stochastic matrix is a special type of Markov matrix where not only each row but also each column adds to 1. Spectral properties of doubly stochastic matrices have been detailed in [62]. For this transformed matrix, all eigenvalues are real and smaller than or equal to 1, with one eigenvalue exactly equal to 1. For identifying k partitions in a graph, the k highest eigenvalues and corresponding orthonormal eigenvectors are identified. The eigenvector matrix of the order $N \times k$ is used for DN partitioning, in effect reduces the dimensionality of the problem. k -means clustering is used to partition the spectral data points.

3) *Goodness of a cluster:* Previously, we detailed partitioning a given LV DN into k zones. In this subsection, we deal with identifying the best-suited values of k . In a real-world LV DN network partitioning problem, we may not know how many clusters we want. We use performance indices for measuring the goodness of a partition and, based on different values of k , identify the best value which fits our needs. In this work, the goodness of a cluster is measured using the *silhouette coefficient*, the maximum of the mean silhouette values of the members in the network clusters. The *silhouette coefficient* of a clustering scheme is a confidence indicator of association between the members of the clusters [60], [63]. Rousseeuw's interpretation based on the value of the *silhouette coefficient* [68] is used for zone selection, and the complete Algorithm is detailed in next.

4) *Zone selection algorithm:* The silhouette value of a member $j \in M_x$ is calculated as, $s_j = \frac{b_j - a_j}{\max\{b_j, a_j\}}$, where a_i denotes the mean distance between member j and all other members in the group M_x and b_j denotes the mean distance between node j and all other nodes not in the group M_x . The mean silhouette value of a group M_x is given as $S_x = \frac{1}{|M_x|} \sum_{i=1}^{|M_x|} s_i$, where $|M_x|$ denotes the number of members in the group M_x . The maximum of the mean silhouette scores of a k partitioned network, i.e., *silhouette coefficient*, is given as $SC_T^k = \max(S_x, \forall x = 1, 2, \dots, k)$. For a given network, vary k to maximize the value of SC_T^k . Note SC_T^k may be high for a small number of clusters which may not suit the application, therefore, the selection of best k which increases SC_T^k , is a design problem.

The algorithm for selecting the best number of zones that maximizes the *silhouette coefficient* is detailed in Algorithm 1. The output of the algorithm is the ideal number of zones for our flexibility assessment application.

G. Power flows for synthetic data

Power flow equations translate the load information of consumers to the nodal voltage and nodal currents when the network topology and impedances are known. Three-phase unbalanced power flow

Algorithm 1 Zones of distribution network.

Inputs: Network details, $SC_T^k = []$,

- 1: Calculate admittance matrix, Y , for the network,
 - 2: Make the electrical distance matrix double stochastic,
 - 3: Set value of $k = 2$ clusters.
 - 4: Calculate k the largest eigenvalues and eigenvectors.
 - 5: Use k -means clustering and calculate SC_T^k and concatenate,
 - 6: Increment k till $k \leq N$ and Go to Step 4,
 - 7: Analyze SC_T^k vector to select the best suited number of zones. The best-suited number of zones depends on (a) how many clusters will meet the required application for which clusters are formed and (b) the silhouette coefficient of the cluster. For example, if the *silhouette coefficient* is very high for very few numbers of clusters, but it does not meet our purpose, then we may opt for a *silhouette coefficient*.
-

equations were used to create the pseudo-measurement point based on the given load data and network topology. Open-source power flow solver of `PowerModelsDistribution.jl` is used for creating such pseudo measurement points [69].

IV. PHASE IDENTIFICATION METHODOLOGY

Using the synthetic data generated using a digital twin detailed in the previous section, we develop correlation based voltage matrices in this section, These matrices are used for consensus algorithm based PCI algorithms developed in the next section.

A. Notation

A three-phase DN consists of phases denoted as $\phi \in \{A, B, C\}$. The DN consists of branches, nodes, loads, and generators. A DN is represented as a directed graph by $\langle \mathcal{N}, E \rangle$, where \mathcal{N} denotes the set of nodes in all the phases and E denotes the set of branches connecting a pair of nodes. For each node i in the phase ϕ at any time t , have two variables: (i) voltage magnitude denoted as $V_{\phi,i,t}$ and (ii) phase angle denoted as $\theta_{\phi,i,t}$. The voltage phasor at a node and phase is governed by power injections. The branch denoted as $(i, j) \in E$ is characterized by line admittance denoted as $Y_{\phi,ij}$. The line admittance governs power flow and line losses. $\mathcal{N}_d \subset \mathcal{N}$ denotes the nodes with loads connected. For these nodes, the active and reactive power is given as $P_{\phi,i,t}^d$ and $Q_{\phi,i,t}^d$. $\mathcal{N}_g \subset \mathcal{N}$ denotes the nodes with generators connected, have active and reactive power generation denoted as $P_{\phi,i,t}^g$ and $Q_{\phi,i,t}^g$. The time t is sampled hourly, and its range is given as $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$.

Fig. 8: A distribution network cluster with measurement points and single-phase loads with unknown phase connectivity.

The DN is clustered into $c \in \{1, \dots, C\}$ clusters. A cluster c consists of M_c number of three-phase reference measurement points, L_c number of single-phase consumers and N_c are the number of nodes

present in that cluster. We assume that all the reference measurements are aligned and there are no synchronization delays² considered in this work. A stylized representation of a zone with $1 - \phi$ consumers and $3 - \phi$ reference measurement points are shown in Fig. 8. DN clustering is performed such that $N_i \subset \mathcal{N}$ and $N_i \cap N_j = \emptyset, \forall i \neq j$, where i, j denotes cluster ids. The set of nodes where M_c measurements are placed is denoted as i_c^M . The set of nodes where L_c single phase consumers are located is denoted as i_c^L . For a vector parameter K , \bar{K} is the mean value, and $|K|$ denotes its absolute value. For a vector K , $\mathcal{C}(K)$ denotes its cardinality. $\mathbb{1}(\text{condition})$ returns 1 if the condition is true.

B. Correlation based metrics

In this work, we utilized voltage magnitude time series as a parameter for estimating phases of the single-phase consumers in each of the clusters. Each of the measurement points is utilized for estimating the phases. Thus, a unique reference matrix is created using the phase voltage magnitudes at the measurement node. For cluster c , measurement $i_c^M(j)$ where $j \in \{1, \dots, M_c\}$, the reference voltage matrix is given as

$$V_{i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}} = \begin{bmatrix} V_{A, i_c^M(j), 1} & V_{B, i_c^M(j), 1} & V_{C, i_c^M(j), 1} \\ V_{A, i_c^M(j), 2} & V_{B, i_c^M(j), 2} & V_{C, i_c^M(j), 2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ V_{A, i_c^M(j), T} & V_{B, i_c^M(j), T} & V_{C, i_c^M(j), T} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The dimension of $V_{i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}}$ is $T \times 3$. Note time t is hourly, therefore, $\mathcal{C}(t \in \{1, \dots, T\}) = T$.

The single phase consumer nodal voltage time series in cluster c forms a column of the matrix denoted as V_c^L , and given as

$$V_c^L = \begin{bmatrix} V_{\phi, i_c^L(1), 1} & V_{\phi, i_c^L(2), 1} & \dots & V_{\phi, i_c^L(N_c), 1} \\ V_{\phi, i_c^L(1), 2} & V_{\phi, i_c^L(2), 2} & \dots & V_{\phi, i_c^L(N_c), 2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ V_{\phi, i_c^L(1), T} & V_{\phi, i_c^L(2), T} & \dots & V_{\phi, i_c^L(N_c), T} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

²Synchronization delays in voltage measurement can be caused due to communication and data logging delays and relative asynchronicity [70].

The dimension of V_c^L is $T \times N_c$. The connection phase of $1 - \phi$ consumers are assumed to be not known.

For the calculation of correlation between reference $3 - \phi$ voltage and $1 - \phi$ consumer voltage time series, Pearson correlation³ is utilized.

Three models are presented for generating metrics for phase identification using a consensus algorithm. These three metrics are described next.

1) *J1: correlation of voltage time series*: The correlation matrix for measurement $i_c^M(j)$ is denoted as

$$\rho_{J1}^{c, i_c^M(j)} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho(V_{i_c^L(1)}, V_{A, i_c^M(j)}), & \rho(V_{i_c^L(1)}, V_{B, i_c^M(j)}) & \rho(V_{i_c^L(1)}, V_{C, i_c^M(j)}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \rho(V_{i_c^L(N_c)}, V_{A, i_c^M(j)}), & \rho(V_{i_c^L(N_c)}, V_{B, i_c^M(j)}) & \rho(V_{i_c^L(N_c)}, V_{C, i_c^M(j)}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Note that the voltage time series is denoted by dropping t in the notation. For instance, $V_{i_c^L(w)}$ denotes the voltage time series for $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$ for single phase consumer located at node id $i_c^L(w) : w \in \{1, \dots, N_c\}$. For single-phase consumers with unknown phases, the phase notation is also dropped to avoid confusion.

2) *J2: Salient features with voltage difference time series*: Salient features in voltage time series could help in improving phase connectivity identification. The use of salient features has been explored in [8], [13], [17]. In this work, we utilize the difference matrix and a zonal voltage fluctuation threshold for identifying the salient features. The difference matrix for the reference voltage matrix for cluster c and measurement $i_c^M(j)$ is given as

$$\Delta V_{i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}} = \left[V_{\phi, i_c^M(j), t+1} - V_{\phi, i_c^M(j), t} \quad \forall t, \forall \phi \right]. \quad (7)$$

The dimension of $\Delta V_{i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}}$ is $(T - 1) \times 3$.

β_c denotes the voltage change threshold for cluster c .

The salient features are extracted using the $\Delta V_{i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}}$ matrix as

$$i_{c, i_c^M(j)}^{\text{salient}} = \arg \mathbb{1} \left(\left| \Delta V_{i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}}(t) \right| > \beta_c \quad \forall t \in \{1, \dots, T - 1\} \right). \quad (8)$$

³The Pearson correlation between two vectors X and Y is given as

$$\rho(X, Y) = \frac{\sum(X - \bar{X})(Y - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum(X - \bar{X})^2 \sum(Y - \bar{Y})^2}} \quad (5)$$

The voltage difference matrix for the connected load matrix is denoted as,

$$\Delta V_c^L = \text{diff}(V_c^L), \quad (9)$$

where `diff` operator finds the difference of adjacent rows. The dimension of ΔV_c^L matrix is $(T - 1) \times N_c$. The new reference and load matrix extracts the rows with salient features in the reference matrix and are given as

$$\Delta V_{i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}, J2} = \left[\Delta V_{i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}}(i_{c,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{salient}}, :) \right], \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta V_c^{\text{L}, J2} = \left[\Delta V_c^L(i_{c,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{salient}}, :) \right], \quad (11)$$

The correlation matrix with salient features using the voltage difference as a metric is given as

$$\rho_{J2}^{c,i_c^M(j)} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho(\Delta V_c^{\text{L}, J2}(1), \Delta V_{A,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}, J2}) & \dots & \rho(\Delta V_c^{\text{L}, J2}(1), \Delta V_{C,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}, J2}) \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ \rho(\Delta V_c^{\text{L}, J2}(N_c), \Delta V_{A,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}, J2}) & \dots & \rho(\Delta V_c^{\text{L}, J2}(N_c), \Delta V_{C,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}, J2}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

3) *J3: Salient features with voltage magnitude time series:* Previously, we used the voltage difference as a metric for identifying the salient features. The salient features when projected onto the voltage magnitude would require the previous time stamp to capture the voltage change trajectory. This trajectory captured will improve the correlation-based metric we are utilizing for phase identification. The new salient feature matrix is given as

$$i_{c,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{sal, plus}} = \text{unique}([i_{c,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{salient}}, i_{c,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{salient}} + 1]), \quad (13)$$

with `unique` operator finding unique time stamps, considering there could be repetitions that will be eliminated.

The new reference and load voltage matrix are given as

$$V_{i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}, J3} = \left[V_{i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}}(i_{c,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{sal, plus}}, :) \right], \quad (14)$$

$$V_c^{\text{L}, J3} = \left[V_c^L(i_{c,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{sal, plus}}, :) \right]. \quad (15)$$

The correlation matrix for model J3 is given as

$$\rho_{J3}^{c,i_c^M(j)} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho(V_c^{L, J3}(1), V_{A,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}, J3}), & \cdots & \rho(V_{i_c^L(1)}, V_{C,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}, J3}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \rho(V_c^{L, J3}(N_c), V_{A,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}, J3}), & \cdots & \rho(V_{i_c^L(N_c)}, V_{C,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{ref}, J3}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

The dimension of $\rho_{J1}^{c,i_c^M(j)}$, $\rho_{J2}^{c,i_c^M(j)}$ and $\rho_{J3}^{c,i_c^M(j)}$ equals $N_c \times 3$.

V. CONSENSUS ALGORITHM

In Section IV, we calculated correlation matrices using the voltage time series for measurement reference located at node $i_c^M(j), j \in \{1, \dots, M_c\}$. Thus, with multiple measurement points in a cluster, independent phase identifications can be performed. These estimations can be taken into consideration using consensus algorithms to be presented in this section.

A consensus algorithm is a strategy that a group of agents use to agree with each other on what's true. In a multi-sensor PCI scenario, there is just one true phase placement (ground truth), which is given as P_c^{true} . Each of the measurements used as a reference for models J1, J2, and J3 as metrics are used for estimating the true phases of single-phase consumers in cluster c . The advantage of the consensus algorithm is that no one measurement point limits the PCI accuracy. One of the most widely used consensus algorithms is in blockchain technology. Consensus algorithms are widely used in state estimation [71]–[73]. In this work, we use consensus for phase identification in a distribution network.

A. Naïve phase identification

The naïve phase identification, denoted as S_0 , uses only one of the $3 - \phi$ reference measurement points, typically the substation measurement.

$$P_c^{\text{est}, Jx, S_0} = \arg \max \rho_{Jx}^{c, i_{\text{sel}}}, \quad (17)$$

where i_{sel} denotes the node id for the reference measurement point. Most literature on phase identification uses this naïve model with substation time series measurement as the reference, see Tab. I.

B. Majority rule

The majority rule, denoted as S_1 , is one of the most commonly used consensus algorithm. It identifies the most agreed-upon estimation. Earlier works such as [74], [75] detail the applications of the majority rule in building consensus among agents (sensors).

We note that for a cluster c , measurement point located at node $i_c^M(j)$, and metric Jx , we can calculate $\rho_{Jx}^{c, i_c^M(j)}$. This correlation matrix is used for calculating the estimated phases, as

$$P_c^{\text{est}, Jx, S_1} = f_{S_1} \left(P_{c, i_c^M(j)}^{\text{est}, Jx} \forall j \in \{1, \dots, M_c\} \right). \quad (18)$$

The function f_{S_1} calculates the majority among the estimated phases. Consider there are 7 measurement points in a cluster. For a node, consider 3 of the estimations that predict phase B, and 2 for phases A and C respectively. In this case, the majority rule predicts the phase to be estimated as phase B. In case of a tie between multiple phases, the majority rule randomly selects one of the phase as the estimated phase.

C. Weighted measure

Previously, for a majority rule-based consensus algorithm, we assumed all agents to be of equal importance (or weights). However, if we use the physical laws governing the system, we can calculate the weights for different agents. In phase identification, earlier works point out that measurement points in geographical proximity will have a greater voltage correlation among similar phases [16], [27], see Tab. I. In this work, we use the correlation value as a weighing factor for calculating the estimated phase. A correlation value of 1 implies 100% correlation.

1) *Correlation as a measure:* The correlation as the weighted measure is referred to as model S_2 . The Pearson's correlation values ranges from -1 to 1. The normalizing coefficient given in (19) adds the correlation matrices for each measurement point and for each phase.

$$\bar{\rho}_{Jx}^c = \sum_{k=1}^{M_c} \sum_{\phi=1}^3 \rho_{Jx}^{c,k}, \quad (19)$$

where $\bar{\rho}_{Jx}^c$ is $N_c \times 1$ vector. The normalized correlation coefficients are given as

$$G_c^{Jx,S_2} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{M_c} \rho_{Jx}^{c,k}}{\bar{\rho}_{Jx}^c}, \quad (20)$$

where G_c^{Jx,S_2} is $N_c \times 3$ matrix. The estimated phases are given as

$$P_c^{\text{est},Jx,S_2} = \arg \max G_c^{Jx,S_2}. \quad (21)$$

Model S_2 , maximizes the normalized correlation values for all measurement locations in cluster c . Note that negative correlation values for some measurements and phases will compensate some other positive values. For model S_2 , the normalizing coefficient matrix $\bar{\rho}_{Jx}^c$, could lead to numerical errors if the sum of correlation across measurement points and three-phases is very close to 0. This motivates us to propose models S_3 and S_4 , which avoids this problem.

2) *Absolute value of correlation as a measure:* For model S3, the sum of absolute value of correlation across all measurement points in the cluster and phases are used for normalizing, given as

$$\bar{\rho}_{Jx,abs}^c = \sum_{k=1}^{M_c} \sum_{\phi=1}^3 |\rho_{Jx}^{c,k}|, \quad (22)$$

where $\bar{\rho}_{Jx,abs}^c$ is $N_c \times 1$ vector. The normalized correlation coefficients are given as

$$G_c^{Jx,S_3} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{M_c} |\rho_{Jx}^{c,k}|}{\bar{\rho}_{Jx,abs}^c}, \quad (23)$$

where G_c^{Jx,S_3} is $N_c \times 3$ matrix. The estimated phases are the column indices of each row with the highest value, this is given as

$$P_c^{\text{est},Jx,S_3} = \arg \max G_c^{Jx,S_3}. \quad (24)$$

P_c^{est,Jx,S_3} is a column array of size N_c .

3) *Maximum value of correlation as a measure:* For model S4, the sum of maximum value of correlation across all measurement points in the cluster and phases are used for normalizing, this is given as

$$\bar{\rho}_{Jx,max}^c = \max_{k=1,\dots,M_c} \max_{\phi=1,2,3} |\rho_{Jx}^{c,k}|, \quad (25)$$

where $\bar{\rho}_{Jx,max}^c$ is $N_c \times 1$ vector. The normalized correlation coefficients are given as

$$G_c^{Jx,S_4} = \frac{\max_{k=1,\dots,M_c} |\rho_{Jx}^{c,k}|}{\bar{\rho}_{Jx,max}^c}, \quad (26)$$

where G_c^{Jx,S_4} is $N_c \times 3$ matrix. The estimated phases are given as

$$P_c^{\text{est},Jx,S_4} = \arg \max G_c^{Jx,S_4}. \quad (27)$$

Note that (20), (23) and (26) denotes element wise division of vector of length N_c .

D. Metrics for phase identification models

In this subsection we propose metrics for quantifying the estimation accuracy, the confidence factor of estimation, and the variance due to measurement inaccuracies.

1) *Modelling accuracy*: Consider, the true phase information in a cluster is given as P_c^{true} . The estimation accuracy is denoted as

$$\text{Estimation accuracy} = \frac{\text{number of correct phase estimation}}{\text{total number of single phase consumers}}.$$

The phase estimation accuracy for metric $Jx \in \{J1, J2, J3\}$, cluster c and measurement $i_c^M(j)$ is given as

$$A_{c,i_c^M(j)}^{Jx} = 100 \times \left\{ 1 - \frac{\sum \mathbb{1}\left(P_{c,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{est},Jx} - P_c^{\text{true}} \neq 0\right)}{N_c} \right\}, \quad (28)$$

where $P_{c,i_c^M(j)}^{\text{est},Jx}$ denote the phase estimation vector for cluster input metric Jx , cluster c and measurement $i_c^M(j)$.

The estimation accuracy for consensus algorithm Sy is given as

$$A_c^{Jx,Sy} = 100 \times \left\{ 1 - \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{N_c} \mathbb{1}\left(P_c^{\text{est},Jx,Sy} - P_c^{\text{true}} \neq 0\right)}{N_c} \right\}, \quad (29)$$

Since there are three base metrics denoted as $Jx \in \{J1, J2, J3\}$ and five consensus models (including the naïve model) denoted as $Sy \in \{S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4\}$, therefore, we evaluate in total 13 phase identification models (the naïve model, S_0 , is performed for J1 only). In numerical results, we will compare the benefits and shortcomings of these models. Estimation accuracy averaged over Q Monte Carlo simulations are denoted as $\bar{A}_c^{Jx,Sy}$.

2) *Confidence factor for phase identification*: Note that models S_1 , S_3 , and, S_4 provide coefficients that add up to 1 (node-wise). Thus, G_c^{Jx,S_3} and G_c^{Jx,S_4} can be used to indicate probabilities of phase estimation. For S_1 , the estimation probabilities can be calculated by dividing P_c^{est,Jx,S_1} with the number of measurements in a cluster, M_c .

We define the confidence factor as the minimum distance between the factor associated with the correct phase and the maximum of the two incorrect phases, over all nodes in the cluster c . For the model, S_2 we normalized the confidence factor with the range of variation of G_c^{Jx,S_2} . The proposed confidence factor will provide us with additional information about the robustness of our phase estimation output. Note, the proposed confidence factor can lie in the range $\in [-1, 1]$ for S_1 , S_3 , and S_4 . A confidence factor close to 1 implies very high confidence in our phase estimation output. The confidence factor for measurement $k \in \{1, \dots, M_c\}$ and cluster c is given as $F_{c,k}^{Jx,S_y}$. The confidence factor for a cluster c for all Monte Carlo scenarios is given as

$$\bar{F}_c^{Jx,S_y} = \frac{1}{Q \times M_c} \sum_{q=1}^Q \sum_{k=1}^{M_c} F_{c,k}^{Jx,S_y}, \quad (30)$$

where $w \in \{1, \dots, W\}$ denotes the Monte Carlo scenarios.

3) *Standard deviation with measurement error*: Q Monte Carlo simulations are considered for minimizing the measurement error biases on phase estimation. For each of Monte Carlo iteration $q \in \{1, \dots, Q\}$, calculate the standard deviation of the measure used for calculating P_c^{est,Jx,S_y} , denoted as D_c^{Jx,S_y} .

VI. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The numerical case study considers a German DN with 646 nodes and 331 loads connected to it. Out of 331 loads, 313 loads (94.6% of total consumers) are single-phase loads. The phase connections are widely unknown to Mitnetz Strom. The objective of the case study is to assess the phase identification algorithm proposed in this work, benchmarked over naïve phase identification model. The selected DN is part of the demo network selected for evaluation in the EUniversal project. For the test network considered, 16 single-phase prosumers have a cumulative PV installation close to 100 kWp. The annual load consumed by all the single-phase consumers exceeds 800 MWh. Mitnetz Strom placed 53 $3-\phi$ measurement devices in the DN. These measurement points will be considered as references used for PCI. The flexibility participants will be provided with a Home Energy Management System (HEMS) which will provide measurements of load and voltages at the point of common coupling. In the case studies, we assume the time series of voltage measurements of all single-phase users are known. In the real world, only measurements of consumers with HEMS will be available.

There are four case studies performed in this paper. The first case study compares the 12 phase identification models on different phase mappings. The second case study quantifies the impact of reference location in a DN on the phase identification metrics proposed in the work. The third case study assesses the impact of measurement error at the reference and/or at the consumer location on phase identification metrics. The last case study compares the phase identification metrics for DN with and without the neutral conductor model. As most European DNs are four-wire, it is crucial to quantify the impact.

Prior to case studies, we detail the test DN clustering results and the performance of the naïve PCI algorithm. The naïve PCI implementation considered for benchmarking uses only J1 as the metric, as most prior works use voltage magnitude time series for PCI. The benefits of the proposed PCI algorithms are compared to this naïve model.

A. Clustering of distribution network

Fig. 9 shows the location of single-phase consumers and measurement points in the DN. We apply the clustering algorithm for identifying the clusters in the DN.

Since the number of clusters to be formed is not clear, we utilize the silhouette score plotted in Fig. 10 for fixing the number of clusters. Observe that the silhouette score is maximized for 3 clusters with a value of 0.872. However, we select the number of clusters to be 7 as maximization of silhouette

Fig. 9: Consumers (blue) and measurement points (orange) in the DN

score is not the only goal. We also need to quantify how many clusters will make the problem tractable by explaining the DN sufficient. Note there is a sharp decline in silhouette score if the number of clusters is increased beyond 7.

Fig. 11 shows the DN clusters. We can also comment that the clusters identified are indeed stable, which is validated by 100 Monte Carlo (MC) simulations. The stability of clusters, impacted due to initialization, are discussed in [76], [77]. Clustering based on k -means is sensitive to randomized initialization of centroids, and if not stable would provide different clusters in different iterations. Observe that the numbering of clusters in Fig. 11 is based on randomized initialization of the centroids, and indeed would vary in a different iteration.

Previously, we defined β_c as the voltage change threshold for cluster c . Note β_c will vary with different clusters, as voltage fluctuation in different zones will vary drastically. Fig. 12 shows the variation of nodal voltages in seven clusters of the Mitnetz Strom's demo LV DN. It can be observed

Fig. 10: Choosing the number of clusters of DN based on the silhouette coefficient. In (a) the variation of silhouette coefficient is plotted with increasing number of cluster. In (b) we zoom into the plot (a). Note the silhouette coefficient is maximum for 3 clusters, however, the best-suited number of clusters selected is 7 [59].

that the voltage variation in cluster 2 is very small, ranging from 0.995 to 1.002. This narrowband is due to cluster 2 including the substation and the slack bus, where the voltage is regulated at 1 per unit level.

Tab. III details the phase mapping scenarios. In the first case study, we assess the impact of different phase mappings. C1 denotes balanced, C2 denotes moderately balanced, and C3 denotes unbalanced phase mapping based on the annual cumulative load on each phase. For the rest of the paper, if phase mapping is not explicitly mentioned, then C2 phase mapping is used, see Tab. III.

TABLE III: Phase mapping scenarios

ID	Cases	Annual cumulative load (MWh)		
		Phase A	Phase B	Phase C
C1	Highly balanced	274.6	282.3	275.7
C2	Fairly balanced	288.6	292.4	251.6
C3	Highly unbalanced	240.4	257.7	334.4

Fig. 11: Clusters of DN.

Fig. 12: Distribution of voltage in phases in different clusters for Mitnetz Strom DN for cluster 1 to 7.

The details of the number of consumers, measurement points, and voltage variation for phase mapping C2 (see Table III) are provided in Table IV. The values of N_c and M_c in Table IV for all clusters remains the same for other phase mappings, i.e., C1 and C3.

TABLE IV: Network attributes for C2 phase mapping

Cluster ID	N_c	M_c	β_c	Max voltage deviation
1	20	4	0.056	0.136
2	73	8	0.008	0.018
3	21	9	0.064	0.164
4	56	2	0.051	0.172
5	46	9	0.049	0.112
6	38	8	0.040	0.091
7	59	13	0.031	0.058

B. Performance of naïve model

As the majority of prior works utilize a single $3-\phi$ measurement reference for PCI, we benchmark the performance of this model, referred to as the naïve model, prior to evaluation of the proposed phase identification models. We utilize 4 different measurement points close to the transformer for evaluating the naïve phase identification model. These measurement points are arbitrarily selected for this numerical experiment. The measurement points are shown in Fig. 9. A zoomed-in plot of measurement points and the location of the nodes of measurement is shown in Fig. 13. It is also indicated that nodes 1, 72, 74, and 511 are connected to feeders going towards clusters 6, 4, 5, and 7 respectively, see Fig. 11.

The results of PCI using the naïve model is detailed in Table V. It lists the cluster-wise PCI accuracy. Note that due to a very small voltage variation range for cluster 2, the naïve model performs poorly for cluster 2. Further, cluster 2 is composed of multiple feeders around the substation, which makes any single reference measurement incapable of capturing changes in other feeders branching out of the substation. Observe from Table V that naïve model correctly estimates the phase connectivity for the cluster with which it is directly connected, however, the estimation accuracy for other clusters can be as low as 0%. This is also shown in Fig. 14. In Fig. 14, the measurement points are indicated by a black square, the correctly estimated consumer phase is indicated by a green circle and red circles

show as the incorrect identification. We can observe that *the selection of a reference highly affects the phase connectivity identification accuracy in a multi-feeder distribution network.*

Fig. 13: Measurement locations for naïve model evaluation

TABLE V: PCI accuracy with naïve model

Node ids	Node 1	72	74	511
Cluster 1	33.33	52.94	100	61.11
Cluster 2	44.44	50	56.76	29.03
Cluster 3	82.35	47.37	100	73.68
Cluster 4	12.5	100	35.14	57.14
Cluster 5	69.77	23.26	100	61.36
Cluster 6	100	0	63.64	15.63
Cluster 7	47.06	15.56	19.57	100
overall accuracy	47.92	44.09	55.59	52.72

Fig. 14: Phase connectivity identification accuracy with naïve model. The correct phase estimations are indicated with green circles, and incorrect with red circles. The location of the reference is indicated with a black square. The substation is marked with a yellow square.

It is clear from the numerical evaluations that

- Naïve model for phase connectivity identification is very sensitive towards the selection of the reference voltage node which is utilized for phase identification of a single phase consumer, and
- Naïve model does not consider multiple reference measurements in a DN,
- The mean PCI accuracy with naïve model in a multi-feeder DN considered in this work is below 56%.

The numerical case studies are presented subsequently.

C. Case study 1: Comparing phase identification models

Previously, we proposed three metrics $\{J1, J2, J3\}$ and four consensus algorithms $\{S1, S2, S3, S4\}$. In this case study, we compare these 12 phase connectivity identification algorithms that are proposed and applied to the German DN. This case study provides recommendations for the best-suited metric and consensus algorithm to be used for phase identification. Note that these recommendations could vary for other DNs. All results consider a measurement error of 1%. In order to eliminate the impact of measurement error on PCI, we perform 1000 MC simulations with different measurement errors calculated using (2).

TABLE VI: Majority rule ($S1$) model for cluster 2

Case	Metric (Jx)	Accuracy ($\bar{A}_c^{Jx, Sy}$) in %	Confidence factor($\bar{F}_c^{Jx, Sy}$)	Sensitivity ($D_c^{Jx, Sy}$)
C1	J1	50.99	0	0.3714
	J2	50.99	0	0.3714
	J3	59.99	0	0.4641
C2	J1	60.76	0	0.3878
	J2	60.75	0	0.3879
	J3	61.14	0	0.4612
C3	J1	58.91	0	0.3791
	J2	59.83	0	0.3792
	J3	59.41	0	0.4628

1) *Assessing majority rule model performance:* The majority rule consensus algorithm ($S1$) outperforms all other models proposed for all clusters except for cluster 2. For all other clusters, the majority rule provides 100% accurate rules with a confidence factor of 1. As detailed earlier, cluster 2 is the part of the DN around the substation. The voltage deviation in this cluster is very small (the worst case voltage fluctuation is within 0.007 pu voltage). Table VI shows the performance of the majority rule consensus algorithm for cluster 2. Observe that all three metrics of phase identification are very poor. Thus, we drop the majority rule consensus algorithm in subsequent evaluations.

2) *Assessing impact of phase mapping:* From Fig. 15, the confidence factor deteriorates from model C1 which is balanced phase mapping to C3 which is highly unbalanced phase mapping. No noticeable PCI accuracy change is observed for consensus algorithms S2, S3, and S4. The mean confidence factor for cases C1, C2, and C3 are 0.201, 0.174, and 0.133 respectively. Thus, ***correlation-based phase connectivity identification tends to be more accurate for more balanced phase mapping.***

Fig. 15: Confidence factor for three-phase mappings for metrics $\{J1, J2, J3\}$ and consensus algorithms $\{S2, S3, S4\}$.

Fig. 16 shows the mean phase estimation accuracy for metrics $\{J1, J2, J3\}$. Observe that mean estimation accuracy is deteriorating for metrics J1 to J3. Further, the accuracy is higher for balanced phase mapping compared to unbalanced phase mapping. Thus, Fig. 15 and 16 are used to evaluate the impact of phase mappings $\{C1, C2, C3\}$ on phase identification. Further, we observe that metric J1 outperforms others. J1 is more robust as a measure of phase identification.

3) *Selecting the best performing model:* For each cluster $\{1, \dots, 7\}$ and phase mappings $\{C1, C2, C3\}$ we rank the phase identification methods based on the three metrics (a) estimation accuracy in % denoted as $\bar{A}_c^{Jx, Sy}$, (b) confidence factor denoted as $\bar{F}_c^{Jx, Sy}$, and (c) sensitivity towards measurement errors denoted as $D_c^{Jx, Sy}$. Table VII shows the consolidated results for metric J1. The best models for a particular cluster and consensus model are highlighted with different colors. For all three-phase mappings and clusters, S3 performed the best for 30 times, S2 for 7 times, and S4 for 8 times. Note, from Tab. VII that ranking estimation accuracy (%) is not straightforward as multiple models have the same value. In this case, we use confidence factor and error sensitivity as the tie-breaker, i.e., for multiple consensus algorithms with the same accuracy level we observe how they performed for other metrics. By using this ranking, we observe that 18 times S3 model was the best performing, while S2 and S4 were the best for 4 and 5 times respectively. Thus, we can conclude that for this

Fig. 16: Estimation accuracy for three-phase mappings (C1, C2 and C3 shown on the x-axis). (a) shows the estimation accuracy for metric J1, (b) for J2, and (c) for J3. Clearly, the selection of metric J1 leads to the best mean estimation accuracy exceeding 96%.

numerical example, consensus algorithm S3 and metric J1 denoted as S3-J1⁴, outperformed all the other combinations. Therefore, for all subsequent studies, we will utilize S3-J1 as the best-suited model for phase identification for the DN considered. Using Tab. VII, we also wanted to highlight that consensus model S3 may not be the best models for all cases. Further, for cluster 2, S4 and S2 consensus algorithms outperform S3. Observe from Table VII that the sensitivity towards phase

⁴Model Sy-Jx denotes that the phase identification algorithm utilizes Jx as the metric and Sy as the consensus algorithm

identification due to measurement error is more than 10 times higher for cluster 2 (close to substation with low β_c) compared to other clusters. This effect can again be attributed to low voltage fluctuations in cluster 2, see Fig. 12.

TABLE VII: PCI estimation performance metrics for different consensus algorithms (S2,S3,S4) and phase mappings (C1,C2,C3) for metric J1

Cluster	Consensus	Balanced (C1)			Fairly balanced (C2)			Unbalanced (C3)		
		$\bar{A}_c^{Jx,Sy}$	$\bar{F}_c^{Jx,Sy}$	$D_c^{Jx,Sy}$	$\bar{A}_c^{Jx,Sy}$	$\bar{F}_c^{Jx,Sy}$	$D_c^{Jx,Sy}$	$\bar{A}_c^{Jx,Sy}$	$\bar{F}_c^{Jx,Sy}$	$D_c^{Jx,Sy}$
1	S2	100	0.56	0.03	100	0.30	0.034	40	-0.067	0.039
	S3	100	0.451	0.016	100	0.376	0.014	100	0.062	0.007
	S4	100	0.436	0.018	100	0.372	0.017	100	0.065	0.008
2	S2	86.8	-0.002	3.63	91.21	-0.003	6.94	85.44	-0.001	4.025
	S3	88.95	-0.005	0.129	87.23	-0.004	0.134	88.32	-0.005	0.134
	S4	91.69	-0.008	0.12	90.37	-0.007	0.125	91.26	-0.007	0.122
3	S2	100	0.479	0.026	100	0.139	0.057	100	0.496	0.026
	S3	100	0.412	0.0144	100	0.26	0.01	100	0.391	0.014
	S4	100	0.387	0.016	100	0.257	0.012	100	0.358	0.016
4	S2	91.52	-0.004	7.259	100	0.14	0.069	99.7	0.034	3.49
	S3	100	0.174	0.017	100	0.25	0.023	100	0.17	0.0168
	S4	100	0.17	0.015	100	0.261	0.236	100	0.161	0.017
5	S2	100	0.373	0.04	100	0.205	0.06	100	0.233	0.042
	S3	100	0.383	0.024	100	0.345	0.02	100	0.245	0.016
	S4	100	0.378	0.027	100	0.33	0.024	100	0.225	0.019
6	S2	100	0.258	0.051	100	0.289	0.047	100	0.11	0.103
	S3	100	0.35	0.019	100	0.293	0.02	100	0.238	0.02
	S4	100	0.315	0.024	100	0.292	0.023	100	0.197	0.022
7	S2	100	0.07	0.096	99.99	0.075	0.55	100	0.04	0.16
	S3	100	0.18	0.05	100	0.1	0.035	100	0.23	0.046
	S4	100	0.17	0.05	100	0.096	0.048	100	0.159	0.048

D. Case study 2: Effect of the proximity of measurement on PCI

The goal of this case study is to assess the impact of measurement point proximity on phase identification performance metrics. The simplified representation of the original network model in Fig. 11 is shown in Fig. 17.

Fig. 17: Zones in a simplified network diagram.

TABLE VIII: Zonal connections

L0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
L1	5	4,5,6,7	5	2	1,2,3	2	2
L2	2,3	1,3	1,2	5,6,7	4,6,7	4,5,7	4,5,6
L3	4,6,7	-	4,6,7	1,3	-	1,3]	1,3]

Zonal connections are listed in Table VIII. L0 denotes the zone where the $1 - \phi$ consumer is located. L1 denotes the zones which are directly connected to L0. Similarly, L2 denotes zones that are not connected directly to L0 but via L1; second-order neighbor, and so on.

Tables IX, X, and XI list the numerical results with mean phase estimation metrics for each consumer and each measurement point in the DN. The following observations are made:

- Phase estimation accuracy deteriorates as the electrical distance between the measurement point used as the reference in correlation-based phase identification and the $1 - \phi$ consumer with unknown phase connection increases,

TABLE IX: Mean PCI accuracy with reference selection

level	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
L0	100	90.44	100	100	100	100	100
L1	100	43.94	100	100	100	99.39	78.78
L2	100	35.71	100	29.57	44.94	75.18	48.44
L3	34.76	-	47.31	27.37	-	30.47	19.55

TABLE X: Mean confidence factor ($\bar{F}_c^{Jx, Sy}$) with reference selection

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
L0	0.372	-0.007	0.256	0.261	0.329	0.293	0.096
L1	0.357	-0.005	0.262	0.141	0.317	0.039	-0.003
L2	0.333	-0.005	0.240	-0.004	-0.01	-0.025	-0.005
L3	-0.049	-	-0.05	-0.004	-	-0.016	-0.003

TABLE XI: Mean PCI STD ($D_c^{Jx, Sy}$) with reference selection

level	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
L0	0.017	0.125	0.012	0.023	0.024	0.022	0.048
L1	0.019	0.223	0.018	0.074	0.039	0.078	0.108
L2	0.044	0.259	0.042	0.099	0.088	0.100	0.124
L3	0.068	-	0.066	0.094	-	0.101	0.116

- The confidence factor of PCI deteriorates as the electrical distance between 3- ϕ reference measurement points and the 1- ϕ consumer location node increases,
- The mean estimation variance increases (implying estimation becomes more sensitive to measurement errors) as the distance between the measurement point used as the reference in correlation based phase identification and the single phase consumer with unknown phase connection increases.

The phase connectivity identification metrics proposed in this work not only quantitatively provide the estimation accuracy in % but also qualitatively provide the confidence factor (the higher, the better) and the sensitivity to measurement errors (the lower, the better). Using these metrics, we observe that selecting reference measurement points in proximity is better in terms of phase estimation quality. This also **validates our zonal phase identification approach** we have established in this work.

E. Case study 3: Impact of measurement error

In case study 1, we identified the best-suited model for phase identification as the S3-J1. Previously, we observed that an imbalance in DN leads to worse estimation compared to balanced phase mapping. In order to not have pessimistic or optimistic phase identification results, we utilize C2 phase mapping. We apply different levels of measurement errors at the point of reference and at the point of single phase consumer point of connection. In order to not be biased by one sample of estimation error, we perform 1000 MC simulations. The three-phase identification metrics are shown in Fig. 18. The three metrics are almost equally influenced by measurement error at reference voltage measurement or 1- ϕ consumer end. Observe from Fig. 18

- Mean phase estimation accuracy for 1% error in reference voltage and consumer voltage measurement is 98.7%. Implying, our consensus-based phase estimation algorithm was able to estimate more than 308 out of 313 of single-phase consumer phases accurately on average.
- For 10% error in reference voltage and consumer voltage measurement is still 82%. Thus, the phase estimation proposed in this work is largely immune to measurement errors.
- The confidence factor deteriorates with an increase in measurement errors, see Fig. 18(b).
- The sensitivity of phase estimation towards measurement error, shown as the variance in estimation in Fig. 18(c) increases with an increase in measurement error.

(a) Variation of estimation accuracy with measurement error

(b) Confidence factor of PCI with measurement error

(c) The variance of PCI output with measurement error

Fig. 18: Impact of measurement accuracy on PCI metrics.

F. Case study 4: Effect of size of neutral conductor

European DNs are 4-wire systems with a neutral conductor is modelled, see details in Section III-D. The impact of modeling the neutral conductor is not assessed in any of the prior works. This is especially crucial if the digital twin is used for generating synthetic data. Fig. 19 shows the phase identification metrics for model S3-J1 and phase mapping C2 with and without neutral conductor considerations. It is clear that modeling the neutral conductor improves estimation accuracy for all three metrics, i.e.

- neutral conductor modelling leads to improved estimation accuracy (see Fig. 19a),
- leads to improved confidence factor (see Fig 19b), and
- noticeable reduction in sensitivity towards measurement errors (see Fig 19c).

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We propose a phase connectivity identification (PCI) algorithm that utilize voltage time series, distribution network (DN) zones, and multiple measurements as references for improving the PCI accuracy. The proposed phase identification algorithm builds a consensus among multiple estimations in a zone. This method is extended to consider metrics derived from voltage time series, which filters larger voltage deviations. Due to the consideration of multiple measurements, the PCI is drastically exceeding the performance compared to the widely used naïve model. Further, our approach is immune to network topology and measurement errors, as PCI accuracy is not dependent on only one reference measurement point. We also propose phase connectivity identification metrics that not only quantitatively describe the estimation accuracy, but also qualitatively describe how good the PCI is. We utilize a real German DN with limited observability for phase identification. This network has 602 nodes and 313 single-phase consumers. It is observed that the original voltage time series without salient feature extraction and absolute weighted consensus algorithm outperforms all the other phase estimation algorithms. The proposed algorithm identifies the phase connections on average of over 308 consumers accurately for 1% measurement error at the consumer end and reference measurements for 1000 Monte Carlo simulations. Thus, the proposed algorithm is robust towards uncertainty with high precision.

In future work, we will consider synchronization errors in measurement while limiting DN observability even further. Further assessment is needed for selecting the best-suited algorithm for phase identification with varying network layouts, load profiles, and PV penetration. Finally, we will extend

(a) Variation of estimation accuracy with/without neutral

(b) Confidence factor of PCI with/without neutral

(c) The variance of PCI output with/without neutral

Fig. 19: Impact of neutral conductor modeling on phase estimation metrics.

this work for executing the algorithms on real measurement data and verify algorithm efficacy by intrusive phase measurements.

Further work is required to consider (a) the optimal horizon of measurement points required for PCI, (b) assessing the impact of communication delays, time series asynchronicity, missing data, and (c) dynamic PCI for detecting topology changes in a DN.

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APPENDIX

A. Roadmap of meter rollout

Fig. 20 shows the meter rollout phases in German. It was expected that by 2032, all German consumers are to be equipped with modern metering devices. (§ 29 para. 3 p.1 MsbG) compared to other countries, thus it will still take several years before the DSO has sufficient data from SMs at its disposal. Complicating this schedule are also the legal issues concerning safety and privacy of smart meter operation and usage⁵. The continued operation and installation of smart metering systems as defined by the Act by the MPOs is thus still possible. However, there is no longer an obligation to install them [78]. This makes the need for DN parameter estimation and mechanisms to enhance observability even more crucial for ensuring the operational integrity of the network.

Fig. 20: Rollout Plan for smart meters in Germany by 2032 [79]

Mitnetz Strom has invested a total of 19 million euros in 2022 in the conversion to digital local network stations. The plan is to install a total of 226 digiONS in the year 2022. By 2026, up to 30 percent of the transformer stations and cable distributors in the network area are to be digitally equipped or retrofitted with the corresponding metering technology. Measured secondary substations

⁵On 20 May 2022, the Federal Office for Information Security (BSI) withdrew the general ruling of 7 February 2020 on the determination of technical feasibility pursuant § 30 MsbG (so-called market declaration on the rollout of smart metering systems) with effect for the past. In addition, the BSI issued a general ruling pursuant to §19 (6) MsbG in which it determined that the use and installation of smart metering systems available on the market do not pose any significant risks.

are an important component in the digital transition. They ensure better controllability and transparency of medium and low-voltage grids, which directly benefits the implementation of the energy transition and security of supply. Increasing feed-in from renewable energies, rising demand for charging power for electro-mobility, extreme weather conditions that endanger the energy supply, especially in areas with overhead lines - the reasons for the digital monitoring and control of electricity grids are many and have one goal: *security of supply*.

B. Real world case summary for need for phase information

Next, there is a real issue Mitnetz Strom faced due to the connection of 8 out of 9 electric vehicle chargers was made using a single-phase ($1 - \phi$). This led to thermal limit violations in that particular phase. With the topology identification, the phase connections were optimized. According to DIN ISO 50160, [80], limits of voltage deviations are defined up to $\pm 10\%$. LV networks are asymmetrically biased by $1 - \phi$ loads. Unbalanced new loads, such as electric fans, heat pumps, and unbalanced charging could amplify this effect. Unbalanced loaded DNs lose a substantial amount of their power transmission capability. In a research project for an automatic phase switch in EV charging showed the effects in charging for $1 - \phi$ or two-phase connected EVs or hybrids in the grid. These findings presented here are also applicable to $1 - \phi$ heaters, inverter interfaced PV, storage, and other unbalanced loads.

In the further evaluation of this field test, it is shown that with the average existing charging capacity, the penetration rate with EVs until a line limit is violated increased from 16% to 47% with symmetrical utilization of DN with approximately balanced phases, see Fig. 21 and Fig. 22.

Fig. 21: Line loading for unplanned EV charger placement

Fig. 22: Line loading after phase redistribution